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Article

Consistency of recommendations and methodological quality of guidelines for the diagnosis and treatment of COVID-19

Abstract

Objective

Since the beginning of the COVID-19 epidemic, a large number of guidelines on diagnosis and treatment of COVID-19 have been developed, but the quality of those guidelines and the consistency of recommendations are unclear. The objective of this study is to evaluate the quality of the diagnosis and treatment guidelines on COVID-19 and analyze the consistency of the recommendations of these guidelines.

Methods

We searched for guidelines on diagnosis and/or treatment of COVID-19 through PubMed, CBM, CNKI, and WanFang Data, from January 1, 2020 to August 31, 2020. In addition, we also searched official websites of the US CDC, European CDC and WHO, and some guideline collection databases. We included diagnosis and/or treatment guidelines for COVID-19, including rapid advice guidelines and interim guidelines. Two trained researchers independently extracted data and four trained researchers evaluated the quality of the guidelines using the AGREE II instruments. We extracted information on the basic characteristics of the guidelines, guideline development process, and the recommendations. We described the consistency of the direction of recommendations for treatment and diagnosis of COVID-19 across the included guidelines.

Results

A total of 37 guidelines were included. Most included guidelines were assessed as low quality, with only one of the six domains of AGREE II (clarity of presentation) having a mean score above 50%. The mean scores of three domains (stakeholder involvement, the rigor of development and applicability) were all below 30%. The recommendations on diagnosis and treatment were to some extent consistent between the included guidelines.

Keywords: clinical practice guideline, COVID-19, diagnosis, treatment

1. INTRODUCTION:

It has been almost one year since the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) outbreak started. As of October 28, 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) has reported more than 43 million confirmed cases and about 1 163 000 deaths, 1 which has taken an incalculable toll on several countries. Until now, there is no effective treatment for COVID-19, and potential vaccines are also only under development. The optimal approach to diagnosis and treatment of COVID-19 is uncertain. Some medications are so far only recommended for patients with severe COVID-19 or in the context of clinical trials. The recommendations also differ between sources. For example, the WHO interim guidance 2 did not suggest routinely giving systemic corticosteroids for treatment of COVID-19 outside clinical trials, but another international guideline 3 suggested that corticosteroids should be given to patients with severe COVID-19 and Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS). Different institutions have recommended differing diagnostic methods for COVID-19 for different populations, which lead to confusion in their clinical use.

High-quality clinical practice guidelines can regulate the diagnosis and treatment behavior of health providers and improve the quality of medical services. Guidelines are also equally important for public health emergencies. After the outbreak of COVID-19, several institutions including WHO, National Health Commission (China), Chinese Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CCDC), the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (US CDC), European Center for Disease Control and Prevention (ECDC), as well as several scientific/professional associations, societies and hospitals, developed a large number of clinical practice guidelines including rapid advice guidelines and interim guidelines on diagnosis and treatment of COVID-19.4,5 However, due to the urgency of the situation, the quality of those guidelines and the consistency of recommendations are unclear. Previous studies 6 , 7 have shown that the clinical guidelines of COVID-19 lacked detail and covered a narrow range of topics. Another study 8 suggested inconsistency between some recommendations of some clinical practice guidelines compared with those of the WHO. To our knowledge no study has yet systematically compared the recommendations of COVID-19 diagnosis and treatment guidelines, for quality and consistency. Therefore, we conducted this study to evaluate the quality of COVID-19 diagnosis and treatment guidelines developed exclusively for COVID-19, and compare the similarities and differences in the diagnostic and treatment recommendations of these guidelines.

2. METHODS:

We conducted a retrospective cross-sectional analysis of diagnosis and treatment guidelines on COVID-19. Before the study began, the reviewers familiarized themselves

with the methodological appraisal tool for guidelines via AGREE II 9 (Appraisal of Guidelines, for Research, and Evaluation).

2.1. Search strategy:

We searched MEDLINE (via PubMed), CBM (China Biology Medicine disc, CBMdisc), CNKI (China National Knowledge Infrastructure), and WanFang Data from January 1, 2020 to August 31, 2020 to identify the diagnosis and treatment guidelines on COVID-19, using the terms guideline, statement, guidance, recommendation, COVID-19, 2019-nCoV, SARS-CoV-2, novel coronavirus, novel coronavirus pneumonia. We also searched the official websites of WHO (<https://www.who.int/>), US CDC (<https://www.cdc.gov/>), ECDC (<https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/home>), CCDC (<http://www.chinacdc.cn>), and the National Health Commission of the People's Republic of China (<http://en.nhc.gov.cn>), as well as Google Scholar and the reference lists of included guidelines. We did not search preprint servers because we wanted to include only final versions of guidelines that are already applied in clinical practice. The search strategy is given in the Supporting material.

2.2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria:

We included diagnosis and/or treatment guidelines for COVID-19, including rapid advice guidelines and interim guidelines. A diagnostic and/or treatment guideline was defined as a guideline that contains diagnostic and/or treatment elements in their recommendations. If the guideline was published in both English language and Chinese language, we only included the English-language version. If there were multiple versions of the guidelines, we only included the latest one.

We excluded the following types of documents: (1) comprehensive or general guidelines that addressed COVID-19, but were not exclusive; (2) guidelines published only as a book; (3) proposals of guidelines; (4) guidelines not for humans; (5) translations, interpretations, and abstracts of guidelines; (6) diagnosis or treatment guidelines for disability, sequelae, complications or other symptoms caused by novel coronavirus; (7) diagnosis or treatment guidelines for other diseases caused by SARS-CoV-2; (8) Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) guidelines; (9) guidelines for which we were unable to retrieve the full text; and (10) guidelines not published in English or Chinese.

2.3. Study selection:

We used Endnote X9 for literature storage and screening. Two trained researchers (YL, ML) screened independently first by the titles and abstracts. Two researchers (YL, ML) independently screened records from the official websites manually. Discrepancies were solved by a third researcher (XL). Full text reviewing was done by one researcher (XL).

2.4. Data extraction:

For each eligible diagnosis and treatment guideline, we extracted the following data: (1) basic characteristics of the guidelines (eg, title, publication date, country/setting, type of guideline); (2) characteristics of the developer and development process of the guideline (eg, the developer institution or journals, whether a systematic review was conducted, whether the evidence was formally graded, system of evidence grading); and (3) recommendations (diagnosis and treatment details). Two reviewers (XL, ML) independently extracted the data, which were then checked by a third person (YL). Disagreements were solved through discussion or with the help of a fourth author (YC).

2.5. Quality assessment of guidelines:

We used the AGREE II tool to evaluate the quality of the included guidelines. The tool consists of 23 key items divided into six domains. Each item is assigned a score from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). The score for each domain was obtained by adding up the scores of all the items in the domain (of each assessor) and normalizing them (score obtained – minimum possible score)/(maximum possible score – minimum possible score). Each guideline was independently assessed by four reviewers. We calculated the mean scores for each domain across all guidelines, as well as for guidelines developed in each country, territory or area separately.

2.6. Data analysis:

We conducted descriptive analyses of the general characteristics of the included guidelines. We used SPSS 14.0 to calculate the mean quality scores of included guidelines. Intraclass correlation coefficients (ICCs) were calculated to test interrater reliability among the four reviewers on the AGREE II scores. We compared and analyzed the direction of recommendations related to the diagnosis and treatment on COVID-19. Finally, we summarized the current diagnosis and treatment recommendations for COVID-19 and examined consistency among recommendations on various diagnostic and therapeutic options.

3. Results:

A total of 37 guidelines were included. Most included guidelines were assessed as low quality, with only one of the six domains of AGREE II (clarity of presentation) having a mean score above 50%. The mean scores of three domains (stakeholder involvement, the rigor of development and applicability) were all below 30%. The recommendations on diagnosis and treatment were to some extent consistent between the included guidelines. Computed tomography (CT), X-rays, lung ultrasound, RT-PCR, and routine blood tests were the most commonly recommended methods for COVID-19 diagnosis. Thirty guidelines were on the treatment of COVID-19. The recommended forms of treatment included supportive care, antiviral therapy, glucocorticoid therapy, antibiotics, immunoglobulin, extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO), convalescent plasma, and psychotherapy.

4. Discussion:

We evaluated the quality of 37 diagnosis and treatment guidelines 4 , 5 , 10 , 11 , 12 , 13 , 14 , 15 , 16 , 17 , 18 , 19 , 20 , 21 , 22 , 23 , 24 , 25 , 26 , 27 , 28 , 29 , 30 , 31 , 32 , 33 , 34 , 35 , 36 , 37 , 38 , 39 , 40 , 41 , 42 , 43 , 44 for COVID-19 and analyzed the consistency of their recommendations. In general, we found these guidelines to be of low quality. Their recommendations for treatment and diagnosis were somewhat consistent, but there were differences in the recommendations considering some specific populations and conditions.

Our results suggested that the quality of diagnosis and treatment guidelines for COVID-19 was low, especially regarding stakeholder involvement, rigor of development, and applicability. This was generally consistent with the findings of two earlier studies. 6 , 7 There are three potential reasons for this. First, in the first eight months of the COVID-19 epidemic, most guidelines were rapid advice guidelines or interim guidance, and the low quality may be a result of the urgency and lack of time. However, the quality of the guidelines has increased over time. Second, some of the included guidelines were published on websites only, reported with insufficient details resulting in low quality. Third, some of the AGREE II items (eg, item 7) are not necessarily applicable to the evaluation of the rapid advice guidelines, which may also have contributed to the low quality of some of the guidelines. In addition, the lack of sufficient and direct evidence to support the guidelines in the early stages of the COVID-19 epidemic also contributes to the poor quality, the quality of evidence for guidelines based need to be improved. 45 To improve the quality of guidelines developed in such urgent situations, guideline developers should learn how to develop rapid advice guidelines in public health emergencies. Guideline users should also learn how to quickly assess the quality of public health emergencies guidelines in order to better guide public health and clinical practice.

An accurate diagnosis of COVID-19 is essential to confirm the suspected cases. About two-thirds of the included guidelines focused on the diagnosis of COVID-19. Laboratory tests such as nucleic acid testing were recommended as routine tests. The turn-around time of these tests ranges from 1 hour to a couple of days; this depends on the version of the PCR and the capacity of the laboratories. Furthermore, due to the low concentration of virus, RT-PCR is less sensitive for diagnosis of early SARS-CoV-2 and presymptomatic patients, resulting in false-negative results. For imaging diagnosis, for different populations, some guidelines recommended X-rays, and some guidelines recommended CT scanning, depending on the population. X-rays have a high rate of missed diagnosis for mild disease, but CT is associated with a high dose of radiation and there is a risk of low specificity. Point-of-care ultrasound (POCUS) has been considered as a safe and effective bedside option in the initial evaluation, management, and monitoring of disease progression in patients with confirmed or suspected COVID-19 infection. 46 A review from Buda et al 47 showed that POCUS could be considered for patients with suspected COVID-19 whose PCR test result is negative. Besides,

ultrasound examination may be worth considering because of its convenience, low cost, and safety (compares with CT scanning).

We found the guidelines to have become more consistent in recommending diagnostic methods, as COVID-19 has become better understood over time and diagnostic test studies have been conducted. Overall, RT-PCR should be the first considered method of diagnosis. In the case of a negative of RT-PCR but clearly ill and/or high-risk patients, combinations of different diagnostic methods for different populations and settings may be considered, taking into account the cost, accessibility, and efficacy of the diagnostic methods.

At this time, there are no effective drugs for the treatment of COVID-19. The most common treatment options remain symptomatic treatment and support therapy. The most frequently mentioned types of treatment were antiviral treatments (59.5%), supportive care (54.1%), and glucocorticoid therapy (54.1%). However, the use of these drugs or options is in most cases conditional, for example, recommended only for patients with severe COVID-19 or for the elderly, or contraindicated for some specific populations. In the absence of sufficient or direct evidence, the recommendations for all drugs remain largely consistent. Our findings were consistent with those of Snawerdt et al, 48 who summarized the results of previously published studies and concluded that there remains no treatment that had proven to be efficacious against COVID-19. But at the same time, a large number of systematic reviews identifying different treatments for COVID-19 have been published. 49 , 50 , 51 Many clinical trials for the treatment of COVID-19 52 had also been registered on ClinicalTrials.gov platform. On the one hand, these trials and reviews can provide evidence for future guidelines, but on the other hand, low-quality or duplicate studies can lead to wasted research resources. 53 In the absence of effective treatment drugs, a vaccine is likely to be the most effective measure to end the epidemic. In the meantime, preventing and controlling the spread of COVID-19 is paramount, especially in low- and middle-income countries and countries with fragile health systems.

To our knowledge, this is the first study to analyze and evaluate the diagnosis and treatment guidelines for SARS-CoV-2 infection. We used a systematic searching method, summarized recommendations, evaluated the quality of the guidelines, and examined the consistency of recommendations. However, this study also has several limitations. First, the searching time was up to August 31, 2020, and some guidelines that are still under development or have not yet been indexed may have been omitted. Second, we only analyzed and evaluated the COVID-19 diagnosis and treatment guidelines. However, guidelines for COVID-19 in combination with other diseases can also inform clinical decision-making. Third, due to the diversity of contents in the guidelines, we were unable to extract and analyze all recommendations.

In conclusion, the current diagnosis and treatment guidelines for COVID-19 are of low quality. The recommendations in diagnosis and treatment guideline for COVID-19 are to be relatively consistent in their directions, particularly regarding the treatment. Up to now, there is no effective drug for the treatment of COVID-19, and a vaccine is probably the only way to end the epidemic.

Conclusion:

The methodological quality of currently available diagnosis and treatment guidelines for COVID-19 is low. The diagnosis and treatment recommendations between the included guidelines are highly consistent. The main diagnostic methods for COVID-19 are RT-PCR and CT, with ultrasound as a potential diagnostic tool. As there is no effective treatment against COVID-19 yet, supportive therapy is at the moment the most important treatment option.

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